

I HAVE NEVER HAD ANYTHING THAT STOOD IN THE WAY OF MY GOALS

Atoyeva G.Kh.

Deputy of Bukhara District Council of People's Deputies

Director of the 33rd general secondary school

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Abstract. *The purpose of writing this article is that even if you have faced obstacles in your life, you should always move forward, set big goals and achieve that goal.*

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Introduction

The birth, growth, thinking, speaking, and acting of the human race is the highest blessing. Because there is no intelligent being in nature like the human race. That's why we should all be thankful.

Now people can be different, different in appearance or in different sizes. But they can all think.

Disability, invalidity – is complete or certain period of incapacity for work due to illness, injury, disability, accidents. A person who needs social assistance and protection due to physical or mental disabilities is considered disabled.

Many individuals who experience discrimination in one form or another due to their disability join groups in response to society's treatment of people with disabilities. They do this partly because they feel free among individuals who share their experiences, partly because they want to protect common interests. Accordingly, they accept the role of disability, if indeed for very different reasons: some, because they want to encourage society to see disability not as an attribute of individuals, but as a result of the actions and neglect of society, which unjustifiably limits their rights and opportunities; others, because they recognize their disability and demand acceptance and respect in their differences this includes their right to fight for equal treatment.

However, most people who have functional limitations in one form or another due to disability do not consider themselves disabled. This creates a problem for those involved in disability policies to avoid being overlooked.

No matter how far we are from the huge mountains, from the roads that are not visible, it seems as if we are standing a breath away from us.

Human life is like that. As soon as we get to know our minds, we step into school, some from school to university, some to see our livelihood, and to leave a good name and a good deed from ourselves. Sometimes we walk a whole path that is high and sometimes low, and we live with the desire to leave a good name that comes from us like a mountain and good deeds that our children remember with pride.

Today, I wanted to reflect on the situations that occur in society, thinking about the situations related to my life.

Because I was born with limited opportunities, that is, because of my disability, I did not know that the sense of health was alien to me.

In modern times, progress is determined by the moral condition of any society, its attitude towards children, the elderly and people with disabilities. Stereotypes against disabled people prevail in the minds of many citizens.

Most people think that the word "disabled" is associated with the concept of "hopelessly ill". Journalists and bloggers - part and parcel of our society - are also part of those stereotypes.

Journalists and bloggers should be convinced of this and should be done in such a way that they accept the idea of a social approach to disability, that is, the idea that what leaves a person helpless is not the disease itself, but the relationship between the surrounding physical environment and society. If journalists and bloggers understand this themselves, they will be able to convince their audience about it.

In my opinion, television programs, films, social videos about the active life of people with disabilities like me and the diversity of their interests should show positive images.

They believe that the media's role is only to generate public sympathy for the disabled and encourage them to provide financial support. Basically, more emphasis is placed on how brave a person is in overcoming their illness or how sad it is for a family to have a child with a disability. It is rarely shown that people with disabilities can make decisions and participate as professionals in activities of social importance.

Research materials and methodology

The mass media cover the activities of public organizations with disabilities poorly, they talk more about their holidays than about their goals, problems or successes. There is no information about the leaders and activists of the organizations. In any case, it is necessary to talk about it, because it is important for people with disabilities, especially children, to have examples of success at work or life success in their lives. If positive experiences and achievements are not covered, they despair and give up striving for their dreams from a young age. In fact, disability does not mean incapacity or failure.

I would like to emphasize one fact, there are people whose physical capabilities are limited, but their spirituality is high, and their spirit is very strong and tenacious. Unfortunately, people with disabilities are often deprived of the opportunity to work, improve the level of education and fully participate in the life of society. In most cases, they suffer from discrimination and “arm shortness”.

People with disabilities usually don't really want to join society. They have a high sense of shyness, fear and anxiety. This obstacle torments not only disabled people, but also their parents. The saddest thing is that people don't accept me because they think I don't fit into the world of disabled, perfect people.

Due to the fact that my mother was sick for a long time during her pregnancy, I was born with a congenital disability, that is, I was born small (short) with a left hand. Unfortunately, this made it difficult for me to communicate with healthy people.

When I was growing up, the opportunities for people with disabilities in society were not good (it makes me sad when I think about it) I was afraid of being called an outsider because people who didn't know me wouldn't accept me for who I was, of course they saw me. I couldn't show it, maybe it was pity, maybe I couldn't digest their looks, I didn't realize that I was human like all other people. When I went to study, I was ashamed of everyone, I was proud if I got excellent marks among my healthy classmates, and then among my fellow students, if I actively

participated in classes. With my youthful outlook, I did not understand that no one has the right to be ashamed of the test given by God.

Because I have a congenital disability, my parents tried to treat me not only in Uzbekistan, but also abroad, that is, in Russia. When we went to Russia, the doctors examined me and told me that there was hope for me to grow my arm. But I did not agree. Because I was not the only child of my parents. My parents are ordinary workers. My father worked as a construction foreman, and my mother worked as a collective farm worker. Besides me, there were my brother, sisters and younger brother. I didn't want my parents' money and attention to be focused on me. Therefore, I returned to Uzbekistan without agreeing to the surgery.

From the first grade to the 10th grade, I studied in the same school as healthy children. I was also the class captain at school. I have never wanted to admit that I am short-handed and have limited opportunities. Unfortunately, the bad attitude of people still upset me. Everywhere I went, people's eyes fixed on me made me uncomfortable. I could not digest the signs typical of Bukhara's: "Repentance, God forbid repentance!" The fact that adults repeated these gestures to each other would destroy my language even more. The society's inability to accept me as I am was the reason for me to resent my parents and consider them to be the cause of my disability.

Due to childhood misunderstandings and disagreements, I was ridiculed among children for being short-handed, and I am humiliated in my own way. As funny as it seems to me now, at that time I was very angry and did not know who to take my pain from.

As a result of the support of my parents and my liver, I tried to never think of myself as weak. My grandfather said, "Daughter, don't lose heart. Although your hand is short, you will still conquer the worlds, you will become a director, you are my daughter, you have drawn me, thank you when you see one, think when you see the other, that is, you and I are people whom God has looked upon.", they used to say.

May God have mercy on my grandfather, if it was because of my youth, he seemed to me to be a strong man who could destroy a mountain. My grandfather was disabled during the Second World War, that is, disabled by a bullet piercing his right hand. He was a great man who grew a lot of fruit trees, various vegetables and crops from his large gardens.

My grandfather's fertilizers and liver scrubs seemed like money to me, and I was tormented by the thought "why am I disabled?" It was very, very difficult for me, after I got to know myself, I was shy of people when I went to weddings and to strange places. All my life I wanted to dance, swim, play volleyball or basketball. I have always dreamed that both my hands would be equal.

I think that because I was young and measured the world by my age, I proved to the whole world that I am no less than anyone else and that I can do anything. I was trying to do all the

physical work with one hand; I got up early in the morning and swept the yard, carried 2 buckets of water from a well or a ditch, milked two cows with one hand, dugged weeds in the ditches of the collective farm with my peers, worked in the fields, picked up to 130-140 kilograms of cotton, flied a kite, played volleyball, I used to put a chair under my washing machine and do laundry, I would roll out dough in a small bowl and finish dumplings and manti, I would try to do everything my peers could do, and I even learned to ride a bicycle.

But as you grow up, my worries grow.

In our time, people with disabilities were looked at differently in the society, I don't know, they are still like that, now I don't pay attention, for some reason there are people who say “Don't dance, they will see your hand”, and I wanted to say to the whole world that I was not limited. It probably inspired me even more and increased my interest in life.

Naturally, like any girl, I dreamed that guys love me as much as they love my friends, that they express their love to me as they express their love to them, and then suitors will come to me. Unfortunately, suitors came to my sisters and friends, but they did not come to me. I think that the guys were afraid to express their love to me. If they don't know that creativity belongs to God, that people are powerless to create the body willingly, I would hear adults saying that Gulnora and her children will be disabled like her. I am grateful to God that I am the mother of 3 beautiful children, both physically and mentally healthy, and the beloved grandmother of priceless grandchildren!

Years, years, years when some of my dreams were dreams...

I get very excited when I remember. When I was busy with complaints, my grandfather told me that they were the reason to imagine my most beautiful future by repeating it over and over again....

So, the fact that I am rich in dreams today, that I have achieved various successes, and that I was able to find my place in life is all because of my liver and grandfather.

The question arises, Gulnora's luck came easily, my answer is no, it didn't happen. The immediate realization of dreams is a dream, the first step is to reach the goal, but if you really want to achieve your dream, you will have to spend all your energy on the way to it. You won't be lucky overnight, the harder you work, the faster you'll be lucky, so it's good if you have big dreams, but you'll have to work hard and work hard on that path.

Today I dedicate these words to my dear, patient mother. No matter who I have become today, I consider it the work of my grateful mother. Oh MUM! My patience, how difficult it is for my mother.

I realized that not only people with disabilities, but also their parents face stigma. What should be done to treat people with disabilities as individuals who can contribute to society rather than “problem”? My answer to this question is this: Disability does not mean inability to work, unfortunately, our understanding of disability is based on general incapacity for work.

I think everything starts in the family, at school. We read fairy tales to children, and the main characters of fairy tales are strong, tall, healthy, unusual people, and rude, lame, blind-eyed, one-handed or legless individuals are negative characters. That is why society, especially young

people, looks at disabled people and people with disabilities differently. Some people consider people with disabilities to be dependent. But it's not. Although I am personally disabled, I can think, work and study like everyone else. No obstacle in front of me can resist me achieving my goals. I can say that despite being disabled, I have found my place in society.

It's funny for me now, it takes a long time for our children, who are admitted to the 1st grade every year in the educational institution I lead, to get used to seeing my hand. Even for some parents. On the other hand, children who ask why my hands are like this are said to have been created by God. Naturally, children ask the question of what evil he has done that God has punished him, as a result, disabled people, as I said above, are imprinted in the memory of children in the form of negative heroes.

Before the introduction of inclusive education, students in schools did not encounter children with disabilities. I think that's why people with disabilities are viewed differently in society.

“If we are not ourselves, then who? To all people with disabilities “Fight for your rights, I say. I'm active, how many people with disabilities stay at home and don't know their rights?”

Discussion

Years later, I began to dream that my life path would at least be an example for my generations. Through the life experience I gained from interacting with people of different nature, upbringing, and behavior during my work career, and through the spiritual food I got after reading the books, I realized that whose if his world is in front of his heart, he will only talk about his world when you approach him. Whoever has goodness in his heart, when you approach him, he speaks only of goodness, and whoever has purity in his heart, when you approach him, he speaks only of pure words. He will shower you with goodness. He will tell you what is going through his heart. And the one who talks about his world promotes it in you and embellishes its conditions.

Conclusion

As I summarize my past life, I think that the small changes and events that have happened in my life have made me a better and compassionate person in every way. What life throws at me does not define what kind of person I am. However, despite all the difficulties, it defines what kind of person I am. I am a thousand times grateful to fate for my life full of joy and meaning.

In conclusion, I would like to say that the world will accept you as you perceive yourself. This is the truth...(continued)

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